

A Generalized Testing System For Multiple Types of Systems Using Automation And Machine Learning Techniques

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Abstract: A generalized testing system would include a user interface for test configuration and results presentation, a test management module for receiving and processing test plans, and a test execution module for connecting to the system under test and executing the tests. The system would support both functional and performance testing, and would be able to test multiple types of systems, such as web applications, embedded software, and database management systems. The system would use automation and machine learning techniques to generate and execute test cases, and would be able to identify and report on defects in the system under test.

Keywords: Codeless testing, Automated testing, Test management platform, Automated compilation and Execution of test cases, Charm.

1. Introduction

Testing is a crucial step in the software development process, as it helps to ensure that a software product meets the required specifications and functions correctly. There are various techniques and tools available for testing software, including functional testing, performance testing, and automated testing. In this article, we review several recent developments in the field of software testing, including a codeless testing framework for web systems, an automated testing platform for Android software, an automated testing platform for embedded software, a methodology for testing chat bots, and a framework for automated black-box testing of RESTful web APIs. We also

discuss the benefits and limitations of these approaches and suggest areas for future research.

Functional testing is a type of testing that ensures that a software product performs the functions it was designed to perform, as specified in the requirements document. This can involve testing individual components or subsystems, as well as the overall system.

Performance testing is a type of testing that evaluates the speed, scalability, and stability of a software product under a given workload. This can involve testing the response time of a system under normal and peak load conditions, as well as testing its ability to handle a large number of concurrent users or transactions.

Automated testing is a type of testing that uses specialized software tools to perform the testing process. This can involve creating and running test cases, as well as analyzing the results. Automated testing can be particularly useful for testing complex systems, or for performing regression testing (i.e., re-testing a system after making changes to ensure that the changes have not introduced any new defects).

One recent development in the field of software testing is the use of codeless testing frameworks for web systems. These frameworks allow testers to create and run test cases without having to write any code. This can be particularly useful for non-technical testers, or for testing simple web systems where the cost of creating and maintaining test code may not be justified.

Another recent development is the use of automated testing platforms for Android software. These platforms allow developers to create and run test cases for Android apps on a variety of devices and operating system versions, without having to manually set up and configure the testing environment.

There are also automated testing platforms available for testing embedded software, which is software that runs on devices such as smart thermostats, industrial control systems, and medical devices. These platforms allow developers to test the functionality and performance of embedded software on a variety of hardware platforms.

A methodology for testing chat bots has also been developed. This involves creating test cases that simulate real-world interactions with the chat bot, and evaluating the chat bot's responses to ensure that they are accurate and appropriate.

Finally, a framework for automated black-box testing of RESTful web APIs has been developed. This framework allows testers to create and run test cases for web APIs without having access to the internal implementation of the API. This can be useful for testing APIs provided by third parties, or for testing APIs in a microservice architecture where the internal implementation of each API may be complex and constantly changing.

Overall, these recent developments in the field of software testing have the potential to improve the efficiency and effectiveness of the testing process. However, it is important to carefully evaluate the benefits and limitations of these approaches, and to consider the specific needs and constraints of each project when choosing a testing approach. There is also a need for further research in this field, particularly in areas such

as the integration of testing tools and frameworks, the development of more advanced machine learning-based testing approaches and for a generalized universal testing platform.

2. Related works

2.1 A Machine Learning Based Methodology for Web Systems Codeless Testing with Selenium

[1] Proposes a codeless testing framework for testing the search functionality of different websites. The framework uses Selenium WebDriver to automate browser activities, a scraping tool to extract data from the website, a parsing tool to clean the data, and an SVM model to predict the pattern of HTML elements in the data. The framework has the advantage of being flexible and not requiring changes to the testing script when a website is modified, but it may not be suitable for websites with dynamic content or heavy use of JavaScript. Additionally, the SVM model may not be effective for pattern recognition of web elements.

2.2 Software Development and Test Environment Automation Based on Android Platform

[2] proposes a design for an automated testing platform that can be used to test the quality and stability of Android software. The platform uses a client module that analyses testing scripts, executes testing tasks, and reports results, as well as a test management platform to manage the overall test system and schedule tasks. The proposed methodology has the advantage of reducing the need for manual testing, but it can be difficult to design a framework that works on all Android ports and platforms. Additionally, automated testing may not be able to identify all defects in a software product.

2.3 Research on Automatic Test Technology of Embedded System Based on Cloud Platform

[3] proposes an automated testing platform for embedded software. The platform uses a Host/Target mode in test mode, with a Client/Server structure. The compile and test analysis are run on the host machine, while the tested program is run on the target machine. The platform is intended to be used during various phases of software development, including unit, integration, and system testing, to ensure the quality and reliability of the software. The main advantage of this proposal is that it allows for automatic compilation and execution of test cases, which can help protect the quality of the development process and reduce costs. However, there may be defects that need to be addressed and room for improvement in terms of the automation level of the testing system.

2.4 Testing Of Chatbots with Charm

[4] proposes a methodology for testing chatbots that automatically generates coherence, sturdiness, and precision tests for the software. The method is supported by a tool called Charm, which uses Botium as the back end for automated test execution. The goal of the methodology is to improve the quality of chatbots by identifying functional defects and user experience problems early in the development process. The proposed methodology has the advantage of being automated and scalable, but it may not be able to identify all defects in a chatbot.

2.5 RESTest – Black-Box Constraint-Based Testing of RESTful Web APIs

[5] presents RESTest, a framework for automated black-box testing of RESTful web APIs. Unlike other approaches, RESTest supports the specification and analysis of inter-parameter dependencies, allowing for the use of constraint solvers to generate valid test cases. Evaluation results show that RESTest can

generate up to 99% more valid test cases than random testing techniques and uncovered 2K failures undetected by random testing.

2.6 UniTest – A Universal Testing Framework for Database Management Systems

[6] proposes a universal testing framework, UniTest, for database management systems (DBMSs). The framework is designed to perform both functional and performance testing for different types of DBMSs. The framework includes a user interface, a test management module, and a test execution module. The user interface allows testers to customize test cases and view results. The test management module receives test plans from the user interface and passes them to the test execution module. The test execution module connects to the DBMS under test and performs the tests, returning the results to the user interface. Extensive testing experiments show that UniTest is universal and efficient.

2.7 Remote Usability Testing of Data Input Methods for Web Applications

[7] presents a web application designed for usability testing of data input methods for web applications. The application was developed using modern web technologies including HTML, CSS, Sass, JavaScript, React, and PHP. It contains various input fields that differ in style, the way they work, and their possible use cases, all of which are derived from real web pages and applications. The prepared set of data entry design patterns was extended to include alternative or auxiliary methods of gathering input, such as speech recognition, autosuggestion, and word completion. The usability testing tool works somewhat similarly to a web questionnaire or survey, where the participant answers simple questions by choosing one of a few available options. The tasks performed by the user relate to one data entry design pattern or input method and involve

transferring values from a table to corresponding input fields. These tasks are grouped into scenarios and each scenario is preceded by an introduction describing the fictional situation in which the input field or method could be used. User satisfaction is measured throughout the test using various metrics, and the results are automatically collected and sent to the back-end for analysis. The tool is compatible with Google Chrome, but may have issues with other modern web browsers. Access to the application is restricted and requires a randomized string generated by the system.

2.8 APPregator: A Large-Scale Platform for Mobile Security Analysis

APPregator [8] is a modular architecture designed to test, retrieve, analyse, and manage information about mobile apps. It consists of four main modules: the Database, which stores all app information the Crawler – which identifies and collects mobile apps, the Worker – which downloads apps and performs security analysis and the Server, which exposes a set of REST APIs and has a responsive GUI for data extraction and filtering. The Crawler uses the Searcher sub-module to collect free apps from various categories in app stores and the Information Extractor sub-module to retrieve keywords for searching. The Worker is structured as a micro-service, with sub-modules for each security measure, including retrieving app components and permissions, retrieving APIs and strings used by the app, detecting vulnerabilities and malware, and performing dynamic analysis. The Worker also sends analysis results to app developers and publishes results on the platform after a 90-day period. The Server exposes REST APIs for interacting with the platform and has a GUI for extracting and filtering data. The Server also has a Dispatcher module that coordinates the interaction between the Crawler and the Worker.

2.9 Architecture Based on Keyword Driven Testing with Domain Specific Language for a Testing System

The proposed architecture, in [9], for a testing system aims to optimize the process of creating and executing tests by automating certain tasks and minimizing human error. It is based on the use of Keyword Driven Testing (KDT), which abstracts the tests to the person responsible for the machine, and the creation of a Domain Specific Language (DSL) to help configure and design new tests without requiring programming expertise. The Tester is able to write a script using the elements available in the "Keywords" and "Symbols" tables, and the DSL will analyze the script using a Lexer and Parser to check if it is syntactically and lexically correct. If the script is correct, the DSL will compile it and generate the code for a new test by accessing the code of the test scripts specified by the keywords. The new test is then available for execution.

2.10 Dorylus: An Ant Colony Based Tool for Automated Test Case Generation

Dorylus [10] is a tool for automated test case generation that aims to achieve branch coverage in a program. It does this by instrumenting the program to gather information about the basic blocks that were executed and the values at each predicate, and using this information to identify targets or uncovered branches. It then applies input dependency analysis and either ACOR or predefined mutations to the input values in order to reach the target branches and increase coverage. Dorylus also includes mechanisms for sharing information between targets and maintaining diversity in the test cases.

3. Conclusion

The development of a generalised testing system can greatly improve the efficiency and effectiveness of testing various types of systems, including web applications, embedded software, and

database management systems. By incorporating automation and machine learning techniques, the system can generate and execute test cases more efficiently and accurately identify defects in the system under test. While there are challenges to overcome in terms of designing a system that works across different platforms and identifying all possible defects, the use of a generalised testing system can greatly benefit software development processes by ensuring the quality and reliability of the final product.

4. References

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